

Study on Improving Flotation Effect and Mechanism of Fine Anthracite by Polyacrylamide, Sodium Silicate and Sodium Oleate

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Abstract:

The flotation performance of clean coal with different reagents and pretreatment agents was investigated. The study examines the efficient recovery of anthracite coal using polyacrylamide flotation pretreatment. The mechanism of pretreatment agents and anthracite was investigated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), zeta potential measurements and focused beam reflectance measurement (FBRM). The wetting behavior and flotation performance of anthracite and pretreatment agents were investigated using contact angle measurements and series of flotation tests. The coal samples were treated with reagents like kerosene, sec-octanol

and pretreatment agents like polyacrylamides, (cat-ionic polyacrylamide, non-ionic polyacrylamide, an-ionic polyacrylamide), sodium silicate and sodium oleate to investigate their impact on coal surface properties and the subsequent flotation performance. The optimum dosage of kerosene was found to be 10 kg/t and that of sec-octanol was 1.84 kg/t. Moreover, the optimum dosages of cat-ionic polyacrylamide, sodium oleate and sodium silicate were 200 g/t, 350 g/t and 500 g/t respectively. The yield of clean coal of cat-ionic polyacrylamide was 70.70 %, ash content of clean coal of cat-ionic polyacrylamide was 11 %. The sodium silicate (Na_2SiO_3) has the yield of 66.66 % and the ash content of 13.9 %. The results indicated that the cat-ionic polyacrylamide demonstrated the most substantial improvement in flotation performance, particularly when used in conjunction with kerosene and sec-octanol.

Keywords: *flotation performance, mechanism, pretreatment, surface properties.*

Introduction

From a fundamental point of view, froth flotation is considered to be a physical-chemical process for separating solid particles based on differences in their physical and surface chemical properties (Urbina, 2003). For the cleaning of fine coal, froth flotation is the most commonly used process for recovering and upgrading coal feed with particle size less than 150 microns (Li

et al., 2016). A typical amount of flotation feed in run-of-mine coal is 7% to 12% of the total mass flow. Coal particle surfaces are generally hydrophobic, whereas mineral matters are hydrophilic (Yadav et al., 2017). The separation principle of the flotation process involves the use of air bubbles that collide with the flotation feed particles, thereby giving the hydrophobic particles an opportunity to attach and form particle-bubble aggregates (Li et al., 2022). As a

result, the gas bubble aggregates, which are less dense than the medium, rise to the top of the flotation chamber where they overflow into the concentrate launder. The hydrophilic mineral particles, on the other hand, do not adhere to the bubbles after the collision and move downwards with the main part of the volumetric flow, where they report to the cell underflow stream.

This study details the work done to evaluate the effects of different reagents and pretreatment agents on fine anthracite coal flotation performance. For this purpose, characterization of the coal sample and flotation tests were conducted to know about the mechanism of the reagents and pretreatment agents.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The anthracite coal sample was collected from a preparation plant of south of Shanxi, China. Proximate analysis was done under ASTM standards on the raw coal sample to know about the sample's moisture content, volatile nature, ash content and fixed carbon (Czajka, 2018). Table 1 shows the results of proximate analysis of the coal sample. For the micro-size flotation of coal particles, the sieve analysis of coal samples was conducted. It was carried out using stainless steel sieves of mesh sizes 150, 200 and 325. Around 500 gram of sample was used for the sieve analysis. Each analysis was performed at a sieving time of 20 minutes.

Table 1. Analysis of Air-Dried Coal Sample

Coal sample	Anthracite coal
M_{ad} (%)	1.09
A_{ad} (%)	22.79
V_{ad} (%)	9.54
FC_{ad} (%)	66.58

Note: where M_{ad} is the moisture content, A_{ad} represents ash content, V_{ad} is volatile content and FC_{ad} represents fixed carbon content

Furthermore, the mass calculation was determined by using the laboratory balance with an accuracy of 10 mg. The results of the sieve analysis are illustrated in the below in Table 2. Moreover, the three polyacrylamides were used as flocculants. Kerosene, sec-octanol, sodium silicate and sodium oleate were used as reagents which were manufactured by Binzhou Shuangfeng Chemical Co, Ltd. The raw coal sample's mineral phases were identified using XRD measurements. With the subsequent operational parameters: Cu (ka) selected, functional voltage of 40 kV, current of 15 mA, graphite mono-chromator, sampling interval of 0.02 /step, and diffraction angle of 5 to 75, the measurements were carried out using a Japanese D/MAX-RA diffracto-meter. The powder samples for an ordinary XRD examination were 0.045 mm in size. Figure 1 below displays the charts and analysis.

According to the Powder Diffraction File card standard data of the primary minerals in coal, the plots were labelled. The mineralogical composition of the anthracite coal sample gained by the quantitative XRD analysis.

Table 2. Sieve Analysis of Coal Particles < 0.1 mm

Sieve #	150	200	325	Pan	Total
Sieve size (mm)	0.1	0.1 ~ 0.074	0.074 ~ 0.045		
Weight retained (g)	368.30	144.10	7.30	0	519.7
Weight retained (%)	70.86	27.73	1.41	0	100
Cumulative weight retained (%)	70.86	98.59	100	0	100
Cumulative weight passing (%)	29.14	1.41	0	0	

Figure 1. XRD Results

The main minerals in the raw coal sample were quartz, kaolinite, muscovite and calcite as shown in Figure 1 representing that any potential variances in the flotation behavior of raw coal sample might not be ascribed due to the occurrence of quartz and kaolinite. The XRD spectrum was demonstrated using the **Origin 2017** software. The three fitting Gaussian peaks, peak 002 peaks, and peak 100 were fitted at respective angles of 20°, 26°, and 42°. The XRD spectrum was used to acquire the characteristics such as peak location (θ), area (A), and the entire width at half maximum (β) (Fu et al., 2017).

Flotation tests

To determine the slurry concentration 500 ml sample was dried and pumped through the filter press. Using the concentration of the coal, the volume of slurry needed for 50 g of coal was measured. Weighed and then put into a beaker and diluted to 0.5L was the calculated volume of the slurry. The needed quantity of reagents was then added to the flotation cell, agitated for three minutes, and then put in a 0.5-liter flotation cell. A mechanical flotation cell is shown in the figure 2-2. After stirring for three minutes with collector kerosene, foaming agent sec-octanol was added to the flotation cell mixture. Stirring for more than ten minutes. To maintain the aeration rate at 0.14 m³/h, the aeration valve was ultimately opened, and the foam particles were collected for 4 minutes. The stirring speed was 1800 rpm throughout the test. The obtained clean coal and fines were purified, dried, and

weighed before being burned in a muffle furnace. The weight, yield, and ash content were used to analyze the samples' flotation performance. The flotation procedure and reagent dosage were altered to quantify and analyze the yield of clean coal and coal ash content under different conditions (Sripriya, Rao, & Choudhury, 2003). To identify the optimum dosage of kerosene and sec-octanol, a froth flotation test was first conducted following the orthogonal experimental approach. In the second round of experimentation, the three polyacrylamides, (CPAM, NPAM, APAM) sodium silicate and sodium oleate were used in a variety of dosages under the same reagent, and the flotation results were compared to find the optimum dosage of the reagents.

Analysis Methods

The coal samples which were prepared before testing were 10 grams of raw coal samples, polyacrylamide clean coal samples, sodium silicate clean coal samples and sodium oleate clean coal samples. The samples were dried and after drying 1 gram of the coal sample was used for proximate analysis. Subsequently, a 0.5 g sample was used separately for Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The other samples (0.5 g) were taken and the flakes were pressed at 20 MPa for three minutes. The obtained 10 mm flakes were then used for the contact angle measurement tests. The zeta potential and focused beam reflectance measurement tests were also conducted using the raw coal and clean coal samples of each reagent used.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

NICOLET IS50 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy was used to examine the mechanism of CPAM, NPAM, APAM, sodium silicate and sodium oleate adsorption on coal. FTIR was used in the transmission mode to get the infrared spectra of several substances. The infrared spectrometer has a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and a scanning range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The following steps were taken to prepare the sample for infrared spectroscopy first, the researcher dissolved a pure sample (0.1 g) in 100 mL of

deionized water, attuned to the pulp's pH value, added the appropriate concentration of flotation reagents at the same time, and stirred the mixture with a magnetic stirrer for 35 minutes. Based on the findings of the micro-flotation test, the dose of the flotation reagents was decided. The precipitate was then rinsed three times with deionized water with the same pH and dried out in a vacuum oven at a persistent temperature (45 C) to enable infrared detection after all the minerals and reagents had been added (Wen et al., 2023).

The peaks of the spectrum map were fitted with the help of **Origin 2017** software. The spectrum map's second derivative was used to determine the position and number of peaks. Fitting Gaussian peaks produced all peak forms, peak heights, and peak areas (Jiang et al., 2019).

Zeta potential measurement

Testing for zeta potential was done with a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS90. To acquire coal samples with a particle size less than 0.045 mm, deionized water was used to grind and filter the dry coal samples that had been prepared in advance of the experiment. Six coal samples including raw coal, weighing 10 g each, were introduced to beakers with a 500 mL capacity, 100 mL of distilled water was added, and the mixture was swirled with a magnetic stirrer for five minutes. After that, various concentrations of polyacrylamides, sodium silicate and sodium oleate were added to the beaker and the mixture was mixed once more. A suspension and sample were ready for use in 3 minutes. The following parameters were used to test the zeta potential value: temperature of 26.5 °C, current of 0.2 A, voltage of 10 V, and pH value of 7.38 (pH of slurry). After the suspension stock solution has reached sedimentation equilibrium, the electrophoresis cup and electrode were rinsed with deionized water and about 0.5 mL of the upper liquid was absorbed using a dropper. To quantify it, the top liquid was then put into the electrophoresis cup. Each sample had the measurement performed three times.

Contact angle measurement

The contact angle measurement instrument was used to study the variation in mineral surface wettability before and after flotation reagents. The flakes of 10 mm were acquired which were then used for the contact angle measurement. The contact angle meter HARKE-SPCA was used to measure the contact angle of water at 25° C under different chemical conditions (Wang et al., 2016). The flakes were prepared under the pressure of 20 MPa for three minutes. From the test, every coal sample was measured three times and ultimately the average value was used as the test result.

Focused Beam Reflectance Measurement (FBRM)

The coal's in-situ particle size distribution in the flotation medium was obtained using the Focused Beam Reflectance Measurement (FBRM G400, Mettler Toledo) technology, as shown in the figure 2-3. A probe-based measuring technique known as FBRM allowed for the measurement of highly turbid samples by inserting the measuring device precisely into the solution and studying how particle size and counts changed over time (Vajihinejad & Soares, 2018). To describe the size, the chord length of the square-weighted mean diameter was used. The value of the chord length often indicates a surge in flocculation production and floc size. On the other hand, if the chord length shrinks, its emphases how evenly distributed the particles in the solution are and that flocculation has not developed (Hu et al., 2020). A total of 250 ml water beakers filled with 10 g of coal sample added CPAM, NPAM, APAM, sodium silicate and sodium oleate and stirred at 400 r/min for five minutes. During this time, the chord lengths and counts of particles were collected with the FBRM probe. The origin software was used to analyze the chord lengths, counts, and micro-morphology of the particles.

Results and Discussion

Surface characterization of coal particles

Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy analyses

The $-CH_2$, C-O-C, and -OH make up the majority of the hydrophilic groups on the coal's

surface. Fig. 2 shows the mineral's FTIR spectra before and after exposure to various reagent regimes. The reagent dosage that was employed to treat the coal samples was consistent with the optimum dosage of the flotation studies. The stretching vibration of -OH is shown by the peak in the FTIR spectrum from $3691.20018\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $3620.24879\text{ cm}^{-1}$, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. FTIR Results of Raw Coal, CPAM, NPAM and APAM

The asymmetric stretching vibration of $-CH_2$ on the aliphatic group is responsible for the peak at $2973.62359\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The stretching vibration of the phenolic-deformed C-O-C on aromatics is what causes the peak at 1054.7109 cm^{-1} to exist (Zhang et al., 2019). The non-ionic polyacrylamide (NPAM) flotation treatment of clean coal samples resulted in much smaller -OH and C-O-C peaks than raw clean coal and CPAM. But as can be seen from Figure 2, the NPAM peak is higher than the CPAM peak and is higher than the peak for the raw coal sample for the $-CH_2$ peak on the aliphatic chain. The peak value of NPAM failed to considerably rise in comparison to the raw coal sample. The molecule, after the addition of CPAM, moves across the polyhydroxy structure on the chain and can react with the hydroxyl groups on the surface of coal at various points, immediately covering the hydrophilic groups of -OH and C-O-C. The peak about 3400 cm^{-1} is induced by

the absorption of hydroxyl groups, such as those present in phenolic or alcoholic compounds, as opposed to the peaks at 2920 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} , which are triggered by the methylene group in a saturated aliphatic hydrocarbon (Chen et al., 2017).

As shown in Figure 3 the peak around 1100 cm^{-1} to 1000 cm^{-1} corresponds the stretching vibration of the C-O bond present in the oleate ion. The peak around 710 cm^{-1} is due to the wagging vibration of the methylene ($-CH_2$) group present in hydrocarbon chain. The peaks at 2921.31 cm^{-1} and 2851.26 cm^{-1} for sodium oleate are imputed to the symmetrical vibration of methyl $-CH_3$ and asymmetric stretching vibration of the methylene $-CH_2$, respectively. The peaks at 1560.65 cm^{-1} and 1446.49 cm^{-1} are attributed to the symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylic group $-COO-$ (Yunta et al., 2013; Najera, 2007). The peak around 1740 cm^{-1} to 1710 cm^{-1} corresponds to

the stretching vibration of the C=O bond in the oleate anion. The adsorption of sodium oleate onto the hydrophobic surface of coal particles is driven by hydrophobic interactions between the hydrophobic tail of sodium oleate molecule and hydrophobic surface of coal particles. This adsorption process results in the formation of a

hydrophobic layer on the surface of coal particles which resulted in the hydrophobicity of coal.

Figure 3. FTIR Results of Raw Coal, NaOL and Na₂SiO₃

Figure 4. Zeta Potential of Raw Coal and Reagents at Different Dosages

From the Figure 3, the spectra of the O–H stretching vibrations related to hydroxyl group

appear from 3610 cm⁻¹ to 3692 cm⁻¹. The peaks from 1439 cm⁻¹ to 1667 cm⁻¹ attributed to the

interaction between the silicate ions and aromatic rings on the coal surface which will lead to the formation of alumino-silicates and reduction in the hydrophilic form of the surface of coal. During flotation with sodium silicate reagent the C=C peak observed in the spectra shifted towards lower wave numbers due to the interaction between coal surface functional groups and sodium silicate reagent. Moreover, the peak of sodium silicate from 900 cm^{-1} to 800 cm^{-1} corresponds the bending vibration of the Si-O-Si bond (Chen et al., 2014).

Analyses of zeta potential measurement results

The attachment process between bubbles and particles as well as the adsorption of particles are known to be impacted by the zeta potential (Chang, Chen & Peng, 2018). The association between the dosage of the coal samples and the zeta potential of the surface of the coal samples is shown in Figure 4 for a stirring period of 3 minutes. Initially the zeta potential value increased to -19.19 mv when the dosage of APAM is 100 g/t . With the increase in the optimum dosage of treatment material the zeta potential decreased followed by an increase. Zeta potential of CPAM increased from -21.77 mv to -20.13 mv at the dosage of 200 g/t which is the optimum dosage. As shown in the Figure 4, the zeta potential of sodium oleate is less than that of sodium silicate. It was -22.49 mv at the 350 g/t dosage of sodium oleate and increased to -21.79 mv at the 500 g/t of sodium silicate. The results illustrated that the use of proper dosage of CPAM can produce the zeta potential of the clean coal particles more negative.

When the dosage of sodium metasilicate was increased, the Zeta potential on the particle surface changed, and the particle surface's Zeta potential electronegativity increased, which suggests that sodium metasilicate was becoming more and more adsorbent on the surface of minerals. For the surface of the graphite particles to thoroughly touch the collector, the dispersion of impurity minerals and their reduction in adsorption on the surface of the graphite particles both benefit from the proper quantity of sodium metasilicate (Hu et al., 2022). To

optimize flotation, it improves the hydrophobic difference between graphite particles and contaminant minerals. But too much sodium metasilicate also adheres to the surface of the graphite particles, reducing flotation efficiency (Bu et al., 2017). The zeta potential of coal reduces from -19 mV to -54 mV when Ni et al. (2018) employ a dosage of NaOL of 0 to 2000 g/t , and subsequently rises to -33 mV when the NaOL dosage is increased to 3000 g/t . The gangue's zeta potential, which ranged from -8 mV to -17 mV , dropped as the NaOL dose was raised from 0 to 500 g/t . According to these findings, coal particles' zeta potential may be made more negative by using the right amount of NaOL.

Analyses of contact angle measurements

The hydrophobic or hydrophilic characteristics of a mineral surface is usually explained by wettability. It is closely linked to the flotation properties of a mineral generally measured by the contact angle measurement. In general, if the contact angle is greater then the hydrophobicity of a mineral increases (Chau et al., 2009). As shown in the Figure 5, the contact angle of raw coal is 48.79° , after the pretreatment of clean coal of APAM the surface hydrophobicity was enhanced and the contact angle increased to 55.87° .

Figure 5. Effect of Raw Coal and Other Pretreatment Agents on Contact Angle

After that, the wettability analysis was done on clean coal of different reagents used in the study. It was found that the CPAM significantly changed the surface hydrophobicity of coal and contact angle of CPAM increased to 69.46° compared to that of raw coal (48.79°), APAM (55.87°) and NPAM (63.56°). Furthermore, the contact angle of sodium oleate (NaOL) is 71.26° and that of sodium silicate (Na_2SiO_3) is 53.92° . The NaOL absorbs on the surface of coal through hydrophobic interactions and form hydrophobic layer. In the same way, the CPAM has also a greater contact angle it is because of the cationic functional group in CPAM which allows for the strong electrostatic interactions with negatively charged coal surface, leading to increased hydrophobicity and the flotation performance. The hydrophobicity of CPAM is relatively greater than the other pretreatment agents used in this study. Hence the CPAM treatment enables the separation efficiency and enhances the flotation effect which is consistent with the results of flotation tests.

Analyses of focused beam reflectance measurement (FBRM) results

The cake structure and coal slurry filtration are significantly influenced by flocculation features, such as floc structural strength and floc size (Zhou et al., 2021). In general, an increase in the chord length value denotes an increase in flocculation frequency and floc size. On the other hand, if the chord length shrinks, the particles in the solution are evenly distributed and flocculation is not taking place (Muhaimin, Chaerunisaa & Bodmeier, 2021). Figure 6, illustrates the slurry's chord length distribution under various flocculant settings. The APAM has a greater floc size. The chord length of CPAM and NPAM has almost the same size. The chord length of NPAM was 25-30 μm and that of CPAM 30 – 35 μm . The value of the chord length of APAM was about 50 – 60 μm . As APAM is a polymer so it has more branched structures when APAM is added to coal slurry, under the effect of bridging flocculation, the particles cumulatively came each other and form larger flocs (Khazaie et al., 2022).

Figure 6. Chord Length Distribution of the Slurry under Different Treatments

As shown in the Figure 7, the chord length of NaOL ranges from 40 μm to 50 μm however, the chord length of Na_2SiO_3 is about 40 μm to 60 μm . The overlapping chord length of both NaOL and Na_2SiO_3 is from 40 μm to 50 μm , this illustrates that some particles of these compounds have same like dimensions in the given system.

Figure 7. Chord Length Distribution of the Slurry under Different Conditions

The overlap is due to the similarities in their agglomeration properties and crystallization kinetics. Moreover, the wider chord length of Na_2SiO_3 suggests that the particles in the system contain more heterogeneous dimensions and

shapes which is from the execution of differences in growth rates, agglomerates presence and polymorphism. From the above results of chord length distribution of different reagents, it is quite evident that the chord length of CPAM is relatively low as compared to the other reagents so the CPAM results in enhanced flotation performance.

Flotation Results and Analysis

Flotation results

The raw coal sample was crushed and grinded into particle size < 0.1 mm for the flotation tests. Flotation tests using kerosene as a collector and sec-octanol as a frothier were conducted at

different dosages. As shown in the Table 3. The weight, yield and ash content of clean coal are calculated under flotation tests having different dosages of the reagents. The clean coal has a yield of 90.71 % and ash content of 13.98 % at the respective dosages of kerosene and sec-octanol. Moreover, by using this optimum dosage of kerosene and sec-octanol other flotation tests were conducted using flocculant polyacrylamide and other reagents like sodium silicate and sodium Oleate. The flotation results of flocculants like cationic polyacrylamide (CPAM), non-ionic polyacrylamide (NPAM) and anionic polyacrylamide (APAM) along with their respective dosages is shown in the Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Table 3. Effect of Kerosene and Sec-Octanol on the Flotation of Clean Coal

Observations	CPAM dosage (g/t)		Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
	kerosene	sec-octanol			
1	9.3	1.84	9.24	79.6	14.56
2	10.16	1.84	21.5	90.71	13.98
3	11.07	1.84	2.9	55.72	15.85
4	12.00	1.84	12.5	52.30	14.45
5	12.92	1.84	7.1	60.68	13.87
6	11.07	1.38	1.5	38.46	38.46
7	11.07	1.84	37.9	37.48	11.77
8	11.07	2.30	30.0	44.69	9.79
9	11.07	2.76	9.30	45.5	13.87
10	11.07	3.23	38.7	58.81	13.56

Table 4. Effect of CPAM on the Flotation of Clean Coal at a Kerosene Dosage of 10 kg/t and Sec-Octanol Dosage of 1.84 kg/t

Observations	CPAM dosage (g/t)	Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
1	50	26.6	78.93	16.86
2	100	7.8	55.31	16.91
3	150	1.1	52.38	20.18
4	200	18.8	68.11	14.64
5	250	17	62.27	16.44

Note: CPAM= Cat-ionic polyacrylamide

Table 5. Effect of NPAM on the Flotation of Clean Coal at a Kerosene Dosage of 10 kg/t and Sec-Octanol Dosage of 1.84 kg/t

Observations	NPAM dosage (g/t)	Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
1	50	13	45.13	18.79
2	100	20.3	45.31	16.86
3	150	15.4	30.25	16.03
4	200	15	43.60	18.00
5	250	21.5	37.71	16.31

Note: NPAM= Non-ionic polyacrylamide

Table 6. Effect of APAM on the Flotation of Clean Coal at a Kerosene Dosage of 10 kg/t and Sec-Octanol Dosage of 1.84 kg/t

Observations	APAM dosage (g/t)	Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
1	50	32	52.03	15.84
2	100	34.3	55.77	14.49
3	150	15.1	46.60	16.84
4	200	40.4	51.46	14.92
5	250	24.2	36.72	15.53

Note: APAM= Anionic polyacrylamide

Table 7. Effect of Na₂SiO₃ on the Flotation of Clean Coal

Observations	Na ₂ SiO ₃ dosage g/t	Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
1	300	10.9	56.47	16.78
2	350	23.4	63.76	16.81
3	400	28.2	62.80	15.87
4	450	21.6	64.28	14.94
5	500	23.6	66.66	13.90

Note: Na₂SiO₃= Sodium Silicate

Table 8. Effect of NaOL on the Flotation of Clean Coal

Observations	NaOL dosage g/t	Weight (g)	Yield (%)	Ash content (%)
1	300	27.2	64.00	13.95
2	350	22.4	71.33	13.80
3	400	24.9	64.15	15.87
4	450	23.3	66.19	13.84
5	500	22.4	68.50	12.94

Note: NaOL= Sodium Oleate

As shown in the Table 7 the flotation performance of sodium silicate is illustrated. According to the flotation results sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃) shows best flotation performance at the dosage of 500 g/t.

According to the Table 8 the flotation efficiency of sodium oleate (NaOL) is illustrated. The NaOL shows good flotation efficiency at the dosage of 350 g/t.

Analysis of flotation results

As a function of kerosene and sec-octanol dosages, the graphs of flotation clean coal yield and ash content are shown in Figures 8, 9, 10 and 11. The clean coal yield increased initially and then declined with an increase in the reagent dosage. The highest clean coal yield, as shown in Fig. 8, was 90.71 % at kerosene and sec-octanol

dosages of 10.16 kg/t and 1.84 kg/t, respectively. As the reagent dosage is increased, the ash content of the clean coal typically exhibits a decreasing trend followed by an increase. As seen in figures. 8 and 9 at the given dosages of kerosene and sec-octanol, the yield of clean coal is 60.68 % and the ash content of the clean coal can be shown to attain a minimum value of 13.87 %. From the flotation observations the optimum dosages of kerosene and sec-octanol were found to be 10.16 kg/t and 1.84 kg/t, respectively.

According to Figure 10 with the increase in the reagent dosage, the yield of clean coal goes on increasing followed by a decrease. The maximum yield of clean coal is 58.81 % when the dosages of kerosene and sec - octanol were 11 kg/t and 3.23 kg/t respectively. Moreover,

according to Figure 11 with the increase in the reagent dosages, ash content of clean coal goes on decreasing followed by an increase. It can be observed that the ash content of clean coal has the smallest value of 9.79 % when the dosages of kerosene and sec – octanol were 11 kg/t and 2.3 kg/t respectively.

Figure 8. Relationship Between Yield of Froth Flotation Clean Coal and Dosage of Kerosene

Figure 9. Relationship Between Ash Content of Froth Flotation Clean Coal and Dosage of Kerosene

Figure 10. Relationship between yield of froth flotation clean coal and dosage of sec-octanol

Figure 11. Relationship Between Ash of Froth Flotation Clean Coal and Dosage of Sec-Octanol

The graphs for flotation studies using various chemicals showing the clean coal yield and ash content are shown in Figure 12. Comparing CPAM treatment to the other flocculant treatments, it can be observed from Figure 12, that CPAM has the maximum yield of clean coal and its clean coal yield increases and subsequently decreases when the flocculant dosage is increased. At the dosage of 50 g/t the CPAM produced the highest clean coal of 78.93%.

Figure 12. Relationship Between Clean Coal Yield and Dosage of CPAM, NPAM and APAM

Conclusion

In this study, the flotation performance of fine anthracite was studied. Reagents like kerosene, sec-octanol, polyacrylamides, sodium silicate and sodium oleate were used for this purpose. The X-ray Diffraction results revealed the anthracite coal sample's mineralogical composition. The mechanism of polyacrylamides, sodium silicate and sodium oleate was investigated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, zeta potential measurement, contact angle measurement and focused beam reflectance measurement. The key conclusions of the study are listed below.

With the decrease in particle size, the CPAM has the highest yield of 70.70 % and relatively lower ash content of 11 % at the dosage of 200 g/t. In the same way, APAM has yield and ash content of 62.83 % and 13 % at the dosage of 100 g/t, respectively. Moreover, sodium silicate (Na_2SiO_3) has a yield of 66.66 % and ash content of 13.9 % at the dosage of 500 g/t. Meanwhile, at the dosage of 350 g/t, the yield and ash content of sodium oleate (NaOL) is 71.33 % and 13.80 % respectively. In the micro-size flotation, the CPAM presents relatively the highest yield and lower ash content at its respective dosage, so the CPAM appears to have the better flotation performance as compared to the other reagents used in this study.

Clean coal samples subjected to non-ionic polyacrylamide (NPAM) produced lower -OH and C-O-C peaks than CPAM. For the aliphatic chain CH_2 peak, the NPAM peak is greater than the CPAM and the raw coal sample peak. Comparing the peak value of the NPAM to the raw coal sample, there was a negligible increase.

When the dosage of the reagents increased, the zeta potential increased followed by a decrease. The results showed that the proper use of CPAM dosage can generate the zeta potential of clean coal particles more negative which can improve the flotation performance.

The CPAM and sodium oleate relatively found to have greater contact angles as compared to the other reagents used. This property results in more hydrophobicity and better attachment to coal surface which will ultimately lead to enhance the flotation performance of coal.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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